

Supplementary Information

A multimethodological evaluation of arsenic in the Zenne River, Belgium: sources, distribution, geochemistry, and bioavailability

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Ad 2 Materials and methods

Table S1 Location of sampling stations on the Zenne River.

Station	Location	Distance (km*)
Z1	Lembeek	0
Z1b	Lembeek	2
Z3	Beersel	13.2
Z4	Drogenbos	16.5
Z5	Anderlecht Industrie	19.9
Z5a	Anderlecht Veterinaire	22.5
Z7	Van Praet	29.7
Z8	Haren	33.0
Z9	Haren-Buda	33.8
Z9c	Vilvoorde Sluisstraat	35.9
Z10a	Vilvoorde Ziekenhuis	37.5
Z10b	Vilvoorde PB Gelatine	38.8
Z10c	Vilvoorde na kanaaldok	40.0
Z11	Eppegem	41.5
Z11b	Weerde Damstraat	43.3
Z11c	Weerde E19	45.0
Z11d	Zemst	46.2
Z12	Hombeek	51.5
Z13	Heffen	55.9
Z14	Zennegat	58.0
D1	De Blauw Bruggen	59.0

* The first station on the Zenne River is located at N 50° 42' 34.679", E 4° 13' 2.996".

Reagents and chemicals

All chemicals were of analytical reagent grade or higher. Milli-Q water (Millipore, USA) was used for the preparation of gels and solutions, as well as for cleaning DGT devices. The nitric acid was used for material cleaning (HNO₃ produced by distillation apparatus Berghof, Germany), samples acidification, and gels extraction (Optima Grade, Fisher Scientific, USA).

The DGT gels were prepared using acrylamide 40% (w/v) (Merck, Germany), agarose (Biorad, USA), agarose-derived DGT cross-linker (2%) (DGT Research Ltd., UK), ammonium persulfate (APS) (Merck, Germany), N,N,N',N'-tetramethylethylenediamine (TEMED) (Merck, Germany) and resins Chelex-100 (Bio-Rad, USA), Metsorb® (Graver Technologies Ltd., USA), Lewatit® FO 36 (Lanxess, Germany), and 3-mercaptopropyl-functionalized silica (3-MFS, 200–400 mesh; Sigma-Aldrich, Germany). The 3-MFS resin gels and diffusive gels were prepared with agarose (Bio-Rad, USA). The $\text{ZrOCl}_2 \times 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and MES (2-(N-morpholino)-ethanesulfonic acid). The sodium hydroxide (Merck, Germany) and potassium iodate (Sigma-Aldrich, Germany) were used for gel extraction. Hydrofluoric acid 40% (v/v), hydrochloride acid 37% (v/v) and boric acid 4% (w/v) (all Trace Metal Grade, Fisher Scientific, USA) were used for digestion. Acetic acid (Merck, Germany), hydroxylammonium chloride (Thermo Fisher, USA), hydrogen peroxide (Thermo Fisher, USA), and ammonium acetate (Merck, Germany) were used for sequential extractions. Zinc acetate, sodium sulphide, N,N-dimethyl-p-phenylenediamine sulphate, and ferric chloride (all Sigma-Aldrich, Germany) were used for preparation of solutions for the sulphide analysis. A multi-element standard solution (Merck XIII) was used for the preparation of the calibration standards for analysis of trace elements together with the internal standard of indium (Alfa Aesar, USA).

Ad 2.5 Protocol for manufacturing and handling the DGTs

The DGT pistons, glass, and plastic equipment used for gels handling were cleaned in 5% (v/v) HNO_3 for at least 24 h and thoroughly rinsed with Milli-Q water prior to use. The gel stock solution was prepared using 15% (v/v) acrylamide and 0.3% (v/v) DGT cross-linker. The polymerization reaction of the gel solution was initiated by freshly prepared 10% (w/v) ammonium persulfate (APS) and catalysed by N,N,N',N'-tetramethylethylenediamine

(TEMED). For the preparation of the polyacrylamide (APA) diffusive gels, 10 mL of gel solution was mixed with 70 μ L of freshly prepared 10% (w/v) APS and 25 μ L of TEMED according to the protocol described in the literature (Zhang and Davison, 1995). The agarose-based (AG) diffusive gels were only used for DGTs utilizing 3-MFS resin gel and were prepared by dissolution of agarose (1.5% solution) in Milli-Q water at 80 °C. All of the diffusive gels were prepared with a resulting thickness of 0.08 cm.

The same protocol was slightly modified for the preparation of each type of resin gel with a resulting thickness of 0.04 cm (or 0.05 for 3-MFS) (**Table S**). The Lewatit FO 36 and Metsorb resins were ground (Pulverisette Type 02.102, Fritsch, Germany) and sieved on a Teflon sieve (50 μ m) prior to use. Only the 3-MFS resin gels were prepared in AG according to protocol by Pommier et al. (Pommier et al., 2019). Thoroughly mixed gel solution with each resin was cast between two glass plates and let polymerized at 45 °C (APA gels) or room temperature (AG gels) for 1 h. The ZrO₂ resin gels were prepared by *in-situ* precipitation on the diffusive gel according to the protocol by Guan et al. (Guan et al., 2015). After 24 h of hydration in Milli-Q water, the gel sheets were cut using a plastic circle cutter (diameter 2.5 cm) or Teflon coated razor blade (2.5 × 32 cm for sediment probes) and stored in 0.01 M NaNO₃ at 4 °C prior to use.

Table S2 Preparation protocol of resin gels (reagents used per 10 ml of gel solution).

	Resin (g)	10% APS (μ l)	TEMED (μ l)
3-MFS* (Reichstädter et al., 2021)	1	-	-
Chelex-100 (Zhang and Davison, 1995)	4	50	15
Lewatit FO 36 (Smolíková et al., 2020)	1.25	240	120
Metsorb (Bennett et al., 2010)	1	60	15
ZrO ₂ ** (Guan et al., 2015)	12.88 + 4.24	-	-

* The 3-MFS resin gel was prepared in agarose and thus no APS and TEMED were added.

** The masses correspond to $\text{ZrOCl}_2 \times 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and MES (2-(N-morpholino)-ethanesulfonic acid, respectively, used for *in-situ* precipitation of ZrO_2 on the diffusive gel prepared from 10 mL of gel solution. The amount of precipitated ZrO_2 in the resulting resin gel is however unknown.

The DGT pistons and probes (DGT Research Ltd., UK) (with an exposure window of 3.14 cm^2 and 27 cm^2 , respectively) were used for water and sediment deployment. Polyvinyl fluoride (PVDF) Durapore® membrane filters of $0.45 \mu\text{m}$ pore size (Merck, Germany) were pre-cleaned in 10% (v/v) HNO_3 for 24 h and thoroughly rinsed with Milli-Q water prior to use. The DGT plastic housings were loaded with resin gel, covered by diffusive gel and membrane filter, and capped by a tight-fitting outer sleeve with an exposure window. Assembled DGT units were stored at $4 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in zip-lock bags and kept moisturized with 0.01 M NaNO_3 prior to deployment.

Elution protocol of resin gels

After disassembling the DGT piston-shaped units, the resin gel discs were rinsed with Milli-Q water and placed in the clean tube. The resin gels from sediment probes were sliced by Teflon coated razor blade at 0.5–1 cm interval and placed in the clean tube. The reagents used for the elution of each type of resin gel together with the elution procedures are shown in **Table SError! Reference source not found.** Since the gel slices from sediment probes are smaller, half the volume of eluent was used in order to avoid unnecessary dilution of trace elements concentration. After elution, the samples were diluted ten times by Milli-Q water or 2% HNO_3 (in the cases where elution reagent was not an acid) and stored at $4 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ until analysis.

Table S3 Elution protocols for resin gels used within this work.

	Reagent	Volume*	Elution procedure	Elution factor
3-MFS (Bennett et al., 2011)	1 M HNO ₃ + 0.01 M KIO ₃	1 mL	LT**, 24 h	0.8
Chelex-100 (Zhang and Davison, 1995)	1 M HNO ₃	1 mL	LT, 24 h	0.8
Lewatit FO 36 (Smolíková et al., 2021)	1 M NaOH	5 mL	70 °C, 24 h	0.9
Metsorb (Bennett et al., 2010)	1 M HNO ₃	1 mL	LT, 24 h	0.8
ZrO ₂ (Guan et al., 2015)	0.5 M NaOH	10 mL	LT, 24 h	0.9

* The eluent volume per gel disc. Half the volume of eluent was used for the extraction of gel slices from sediment probes.

** LT – Laboratory temperature (20 °C).

DGT calculations

Arsenic mass (M , ng) accumulated on the resin gel disc is calculated from the concentration of As measured by analytical technique in the eluent (c_e) using (1), where V is the total volume of gel and elution agent and f_e is the elution factor.

$$M = c_e \cdot V / f_e \quad (1)$$

Arsenic concentration determined by DGT (c_{DGT} , $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) is then calculated from the accumulated mass (M , ng), the thickness of diffusive layer consisting of diffusive gel and membrane filter (Δg , cm), the diffusion coefficient of As (D , $\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$), the area of the exposure window (A , cm^2), and the deployment time (t , s) using (2).

$$c_{DGT} = M \cdot \Delta g / (D \cdot A \cdot t) \quad (2)$$

The diffusion coefficients of As at 25 °C used for calculations were as follows – $6.41 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ for Lewatit FO 36 (Smolíková et al., 2020), $10.1 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ for 3-MFS (As^{III}) (Bennett et al., 2010), 6.78×10^{-6} for ZrO₂ (Guan et al., 2015), and $5.96 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ for Metsorb (measured in the laboratory).

Ad 3 Results and discussion

Ad 3.1 Distribution of dissolved and particulate As in water along the Zenne River

Fig. S1 Longitudinal profiles of the SPM (A), pH (B), and conductivity (C) along the Zenne River (0 km corresponds to station Z1 in Lembeek).

Ad 3.2 Temporal variability of As concentrations in the Zenne River

Ad 3.2.1 Influence of the weather conditions

Fig. S2 Variation of the dissolved (A) and particulate (B) As concentrations during the dry periods at stations Z3, Z4, Z7, and Z9 with distribution coefficients of As (C) and percentage of dissolved As (D).

Z3 (10-12/09/2013)

A

B

C

D

Z9 (03/10/2012)

Fig. S3 Variation of the dissolved (A) and particulate (B) As concentrations during two rain events at stations Z3 and Z9 with distribution coefficients of As (C) and percentage of dissolved As (D) (yellow areas highlighting periods with increasing discharge).

Ad 3.2.3 Influence of the tidal cycle

Fig. S4 Variation profiles of conductivity (A), pH (B), dissolved oxygen concentrations (C) and suspended particulate matter (D) at Z14 (Zennegat) during a tidal cycle, March 2021.

Ad 3.3 Source of As elevated concentrations in the downstream part of the Zenne River

Table S4 Average daily waterflow and dissolved arsenic concentrations (As-dis) used in the mass balance.

Station	Waterflow ($\text{m}^3 \text{d}^{-1}$)	Provider	As-dis ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)	Provider
Zenne:				
Zenne-Z9	754,872	Flowbru 2010-2016 (1)	1.29 (0.26)	this study + additional measurements (5)
Zenne-Z11	855,207	Waterinfo 2010-2016 (2)	9.5 (5.1)	this study + additional measurements (5)
To Zenne:				
Woluwe outlet	40,515	OSIRIS water mass balance (3)	1.45 (0.59)	additional measurements (5)
Tangebeek outlet	27,993	OSIRIS water mass balance (3)	176 (58)	VMM (4)
Canal overflow	21,105	OSIRIS water mass balance (3)	2.06 (0.38)	additional measurements (5)
CSO	3,858	VMM (4)	1.29 (0.29)	additional measurements (6)
To Tangebeek:				
CSO	34	VMM (4)	1.29 (0.29)	additional measurements (6)

(1) www.flowbru.be; (2) www.waterinfo.be; (3) Carbonnel et al. 2016 (Carbonnel et al., 2016); (4) Vlaamse Milieu Maatschappij, www.geoloket.vmm.be/Geoviews/; (5) performed by the authors between 2010 and 2016; (6) performed by the authors between 2010 and 2016 in untreated sewage from Brussels. The As-dis values are averages for the period 2010–2016 with standard deviations in brackets. CSO – combined sewer overflow.

Fig. S5 Evolution of dissolved and total As concentrations (As-dis, As-tot) during 2008-2020 at stations Lembeek, Anderlecht, Haren, Epegem, Heffen, Dijle, and Tangebeek based on the data from VMM online database (data expressed as median values with 10th (P10) and 90th (P90) percentiles for $n = 5-12$).

Ad 3.4.2 Sequential extractions of sediments along the Zenne River

Fig. S6 Iron, manganese, and arsenic sequential extractions of sediments in the Brussels region and the tidal Zenne, 2013 (F1 – exchangeable and carbonate fraction; F2 – reducible fraction; F3 – oxidisable fraction; F4 – residual fraction).

Ad 3.4.3 The dissolved and labile As, Fe, and Mn concentrations in porewater

Fig. S7 The depth profiles of redox potential and pH in the sediments at stations Z5 and Z14 (June 2020).

Ad 3.4.4 Diffusive benthic fluxes of As

Table S5 Data used for calculations of benthic fluxes of arsenic with resulting fluxes calculated for zones Z1–Z10 and Z11–Z14.

	Porosity	D_{sed} ($\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$)	dC / dx	F_D ($\mu\text{g m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$)	Zone	Area (km^2)	Flux (g d^{-1})
Z5	0.6	4.55×10^{-6}	6	14.2	Z1–Z10	0.35	5
Z14	0.85	6.94×10^{-6}	45	229	Z11–Z14	0.23	53

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